

Mechanisms of heat storage and trend in the Mediterranean Sea in a high emission CMIP6 scenario with the regional climate system model CNRM-RCSM6.

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CNRM-RCSM6 configuration : model components

- ALADIN_Climate V6 (Daniel et al., 2018) : interactive TACTIC aerosol scheme (Nabat et al., 2015) direct and indirect effects
- SURFEX v8 (Masson et al. 2013, Voldoire et al. 2017) : lake model FLAKE
- CTRIP (Decharme et al., 2010) : floodplains, groundwater diffusive scheme, variable velocity
- NEMOMED12 (Beuvier et al., 2012 for v3.2) : regional version of NEMOv3.6 (Madec et al., 2008), new physics
- OASIS3-MCT (Craig et al., 2017)

Scientific choices

- CRNM-RCSM6 :
 - Follow the last version of the CNRM GCM, used for the CMIP6 intercomparison (*Voltaire et al., 2017*): ALADIN-Climate V6, CTRIP, SURFEX v8, OASIS3-MCT
 - Follow the MedCORDEX recommendations for the inter-comparison
- A CMIP6 historical and SSP5-8.5 scenario driven by CNRM-ESM2-1 simulation :
 - Temperature and Salinity unbiased in the Atlantic zone of NEMOMED12 (CNRM-ESM2-1 too cold and fresh)
 - 79 years of coupled spin-up, initial condition MEDHYMAPv2.2 1970-1980 average (ORAS4 in the Atlantic part)
 - A 1980-2100 control simulation (years 1950-1979 in a random order every 30-yr period)

CNRM-RCSM

Context

- New CMIP6 high emission scenarios show more pronounced Sea Surface Temperature trends for the Mediterranean Sea
- MedECC report (CMIP5, RCP85, [2071-2100] - [1976-2005]): MED [2.7 to 3 .8] °C at the end of the century
- CMIP6 SSP585 global scenario ([2071-2100] - [1985-2014]): MED [2.1 to 5.2] °C
- Regional CNRM-RCSM simulations :

Context

Average MED SST

Average MED T3D

Obs in grey hindcast in red, control in black, CNRM-RCSM6 in blue

- A well-balanced simulation, with a stable control
- follows the observed trend in the historical simulation
- a slowdown in the middle of the period
- a new positive trend after 2060

Scientific question

- What drives the trend of heat content of the Mediterranean under this high-emission scenario ?
- **Method** : For all variable V we compute the integrated anomaly to the control simulation :
 - $\text{integr_anom}(\text{yr}) = \sum_{(y=1980 \text{ to } \text{yr})} (V_{\text{RCSM6}}(y) - \bar{V}_{\text{CTRL}})$
 - Transformation $\text{W/m}^2 \rightarrow \text{°C} : 1\text{W/m}^2 \leftrightarrow 0,0051 \text{°C/yr}$

Heat balance of the model

Integrated Med Sea anomalies of heat content, net surface flux, and net gibraltar heat inflow, in °C

- T3D anomaly = (surf flux + Gibraltar heat inflow) anomalies + residual
- final residual = -0.0002 °C/yr
- Gibraltar Strait heat inflow and surface fluxes are equally important until 2060
- the lowering of Gib. inflow after 2060 limits the trends of T3D

a- Decomposition of the Surface heat flux

Integrated anomalies to the control of each term of the surface flux

→ lowering of net heat loss through the Med surface due to less longwave and less sensible heat loss to the atmosphere

b- Decomposition of the net heat flux at Gibraltar (1)

Gibraltar heat flux anomaly $UT_{RCSM6} - UT_{Ctr}$
= $(UT)'$
= **term 1** due to anomaly of transport $U'T$
+ **term 2** due to anomaly of temperature UT'
+ **term 3** due to covariance of $U'T'$ anomalies

- The difference of temperature drives (term UT')
- the anomaly of volume transport always positive (term $U'T$) : more net volume flux due to the evaporation

b- Decomposition of the net heat flux at Gibraltar (2)

Gibraltar heat flux anomaly $UT_{RCSM6} - UT_{Ctr}$

= (UT)'

= **term 1** due to anomaly of transport U'T

+ **term 2** due to anomaly of temperature $UT' = \text{inflow (Atl to Med)} + \text{outflow (Med to Atl)}$

+ **term 3** due to covariance of U'T' anomalies

Integration of each term with UT' in and out

- The difference of temperature drives (term UT')
- the anomaly of volume transport always positive : more net volume flux due to the evaporation
- the inflow temperature is important in the beginning
- then the outflow of warmer water causes the slowing of Gibraltar input

Conclusion

- CNRM-RCSM6 historical and scenario simulation under the CMIP6-SSP585 CNRM-ESM2-1 forcing
- A stable control simulation
- An novel decomposition of the terms involved in the heat budget of the Mediterranean
- What drives the trend of heat content of the Mediterranean under the scenario ?
 - The surface heat flux is the major driver for the long term trend of heat content, the Gibraltar Strait the second one
 - Gibraltar Strait heat inflow and surface fluxes are equally important until 2060
 - After 2060 the outflow of warmer water causes the slowing of Gibraltar input and limits the heating of the MED

Trend of heat content

Decomposition of the net heat flux at Gibraltar (1)

- Gibraltar heat flux through the vertical section of the Strait = $\Sigma U(z)*T(z) * \text{area}(z) = \ll \text{in} \gg + \ll \text{out} \gg$
- from Atl to Med : $\ll \text{in} \gg = \Sigma_{U>0} U(z)*T(z) * \text{area}(z)$
- from Med to Atl : $\ll \text{out} \gg = \Sigma_{U<0} U(z)*T(z) * \text{area}(z)$

Integrated anomalies to the control

- The inflow rises : the Atlantic brings heat to the Med
- The inflow dominates until 2060
- After 2060, the outflow takes the lead,
→ Less net heat income

Trend of heat content

Method

- Knowing that $dT_{3D}/dt = GIBRin - GIBRout + Q_{sw} + Q_{lw} + Q_s + Q_l + residual$:
which term drives ?
- Control run budget closed : residual = $-0.0005^\circ\text{C}/\text{yr}$
- For all variable V we compute the integrated anomaly to the control simulation :
 - $integr_anom(yr) = \sum_{(y=1980 \text{ to } yr)} (V_{RCSM6}(y) - \bar{V}_{CTRL})$
- Transformation $\text{W}/\text{m}^2 \rightarrow ^\circ\text{C} : 1\text{W}/\text{m}^2 \leftrightarrow 0,51 ^\circ\text{C}/100\text{yr}$

What happens at the Gibraltar Strait ? A view of the lon=5.5°W section

Zonal current

(not anomaly)

Few changes in the current

Temperature

Strong warm anomaly in the Outgoing water

→ The intensification of the net heat outflow comes from the Mediterranean Outflow Water